

EFFECT OF GUTTING ON SENSORY, SOME BIOCHEMICAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF NILE PERCH (*Lates niloticus*) AND NILE TILAPIA (*Oreochromis niloticus*) STORED IN ICE

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ABSTRACT

Guts are generally recognized as sources of bacteria in fish. However, effects of gutting on sensory, biochemical and microbiological properties of Nile Tilapia and Nile perch are generally not known. This work was done in order to understand how sensory properties, some biochemical and microbiological indices varied during iced storage. Three fish each from the gutted and ungutted lots were randomly sampled on days 2, 6, 10, 14, 18, 22, 26 and 30, but also on day 34 for farmed tilapia. All samples were analyzed for changes in selected sensory parameters, FFA, TVBN, pH, and hydrogen sulphide-producing bacteria, coliforms and *Escherichia coli*. Results at rejection were 2.4-2.7 % FFA, 25-27 mg N/100 g flesh as TVBN, pH 7.1-7.2 and CFU/100 g flesh of log 5.0 and 6.5 H₂S-producing bacteria in ungutted Tilapia and Nile perch, respectively. H₂S-producing bacterial load was log 5.3 and 5.5 for gutted Tilapia and Nile perch, respectively, at rejection. Coliforms at rejection of ungutted fish were log 5.1, but log 2.1 and 1.8 in gutted Tilapia and Nile perch, respectively. *E. coli* were not detected in any experimental fish. Gutting increased shelf life by 4 days in both fish. At rejection, biochemical and microbiological indices were of comparable magnitude in ungutted and gutted samples of both fish, but were lower in gutted lots. Gutting slowed the rate of change of sensory, biochemical and microbiological parameters and indices, respectively.

KEYWORDS: Gutting, Nile tilapia, Nile perch, sensory, microbiological, biochemical properties

INTRODUCTION

In 2005 and 2009, Kenya's inland fishery produced 139,062 and 133,600 metric tons of fresh fish, respectively (MOFD 2005, 2009). In the inland fishery, the Nile perch (*Lates niloticus*) (the major export commodity) and Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) from L. Victoria combined catch was 42.3% of the total annual fish capture output. Despite the Nile perch being an important foreign exchange earner in the export market, together with the Nile tilapia, they are important commodities in national commerce, nutrition and food security for Kenya's riparian communities. Despite the national importance of the two fish species, there is little information available on changes in their sensory quality and in the accompanying biochemical and microbiological changes when they are stored in ice in the gutted and ungutted state. The quality of fresh fish is a major concern to the fish industry and consumers alike. Like marine fish, fresh water fish are highly perishable commodities. Deterioration in the quality of fish occurs due to the effect of a variety of biochemical and microbial mechanisms. However, the rate of loss of quality depends directly on the nature of the fish species and on the handling and storage conditions (Olafsdottir *et al.*, 1997).

Storage time and handling conditions have great impact on the sensory, biochemical and microbiological quality of fish and fish products. The rate of deterioration of fish is highly temperature dependent, and can be inhibited by the use of low storage temperature (Kraus, 1992). Icing reduces the temperature of fish and therefore lowers the growth of spoilage and pathogenic micro-organisms and hence their spoilage rate. Also, as the gut is a major holder of a large number of microorganisms in fish, it is normally believed that the removal of gut material, especially the intestines, reduces the bacterial load responsible for the deterioration of fish and the subsequent fish products.

A major objective of this study was, therefore, to assess the effect of storage in ice and gutting on the sensory, some biochemical and microbiological quality of the 2 fish species and to study the usefulness of selected sensory, microbiological and biochemical parameters in determining their shelf life in ice. The selected microbiological and biochemical indices were deemed useful for establishing the deterioration profile of gutted and iced Nile perch and Tilapia, which are the among the three most important fish species of Kenya's inland fishery. The changes in sensory properties were studied using the quality index method (QIM). The QIM is a systematic procedure that allows rapid and easy evaluation of attributes of raw fish during storage. The technique is relatively fast and is based only on direct observations of fish attributes. It is more precise and specific than other methods since it is species-specific. A demerit score, ranging from 0-3, is applied to each attribute (Corlett, 1998). According to studies done in other countries, it has been found that in most fish species, changes in quality index (QI) scores highly correlate with the time of storage in ice (Huss, 1995). To evaluate the freshness of a specific species, the parameters and characters are defined by descriptive analysis. A precise description of these high-impact characteristics is done. Also, only those attributes that mirror the deterioration profile and loss of quality of fish during storage, are used to develop the QI scheme. Once characters and descriptors are defined, the QIM becomes a reliable sensory tool for assessing fish freshness, and related biochemical and microbiological quality changes.

The biochemical indices of deterioration that were examined included total volatile basic nitrogen (TVBN), pH, % free fatty acids (FFA) (as oleic acid), while the microbiological indices selected for study included the total viable count (TVC) at 22 and 37 °C, coliforms, E. coli, and hydrogen sulphide producing bacteria counts at 22 °C for the 2 fish species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Raw material and sampling

Fresh Nile perch (*Lates niloticus*) were purchased at random from fishermen at Dunga and Ogal fish landing sites situated about 2 and 30 km, respectively, from Kisumu City, Kenya, between December 2009 and February, 2010. Two batches of Nile tilapia were also bought at Usenge beach in Bondo County, Kenya, in March and April 2010. Two latter batches of Nile tilapia and controls were purchased from Dominion Farms aquaculture ponds in Siaya County in May and July 2010. The time interval between harvesting and arrival of the Nile perch at the landing sites was estimated to be about 4 hr. The controls for the Nile perch were iced immediately after being taken off the nets at the fishing ground by the fishermen according to our instructions. The controls for the Nile tilapia were iced 1 hr after harvest from the aquaculture ponds. After taking the weights and lengths (controlled) of the beach-purchased fish, the fish samples were divided into two groups with one group ungutted and the other gutted. The gutting process was hygienically done at the landing beaches. Both ungutted and gutted Nile perch and tilapia were washed with running drinking tap water to remove any dirt or slime and were immediately layered with flaked ice and hygienically packed in insulated containers. The iced fish were transported to a nearby chill store and stored at 0-2°C overnight before being transported the following day within 4-5 hr to cold rooms at Egerton University, 150 km away, where they were stored at 0-2 °C throughout the experimental period. Three fish (the experimental unit) each of both gutted and ungutted fish were randomly sampled on days 2, 6, 10, 14, 18 and 22, 26 and 30 for both controls and experimental Nile perch and tilapia. The farmed tilapia was stored and sampled for up to 34 days. All experimental and control fish samples were analyzed according to the sensory, biochemical and microbiological procedures described in the sections that follow.

Limitations of the study: Some of the limitations experienced in the course of the study included:

1. Due to the difficulty of obtaining adequate amounts of the Nile tilapia on the fishing grounds (as was done for the Nile perch), due to the depletion of the natural resource, farmed tilapia were used as controls. However, despite that, there were little or no differences in the pattern of change of sensory, biochemical and microbiological parameters according to the study when using either the farmed tilapia or the lake tilapia as experimental samples, except for the longer shelf life in the farmed Tilapia.
2. The time interval between harvest of the fish on the fishing grounds and arrival at the beach was estimated to be 4-5 hr but this could be as long as 6 hr. The estimate of time by the fishermen was assumed to apply. As expected, naturally not all the fish used in the study were caught in the gill nets at the same time.

Sensory Evaluation

The changes in the sensory parameters of the two fish species were assessed over the storage period of 30 days and on the 34th day for farmed Tilapia by a panel of ten previously trained assessors belonging to the Department of Dairy and Food Science and Technology of Egerton University, Kenya. The appearance of the skin; skin slime color; clarity and shape of the eyes; skin elasticity; belly integrity, gill colour, odour and gill slime appearance were assessed based on scores of 0-3 (Table 1). The attributes of cooked fish (odour, taste and texture) were evaluated by the same laboratory expert panel of ten people on each sampling day, simultaneously. The odour, taste and texture were evaluated using a structured acceptability scale of 0-10 with the rejection threshold set at 4.

Biochemical analyses

Total volatile basic nitrogen (TVBN)

Approximately 10 g of skinless fish flesh from the tail region was homogenized with 50 mL of distilled water. The mixture was centrifuged in a Sorval RC-285 centrifuge (Dupont, Wilmington, Delaware, U.S.A) at 400 rpm for 5 min and the supernatant filtered through a Büchner funnel using Whatman No.1 filter paper. Two grams of MgO was added followed by one drop of antifoaming agent. A 250-mL Erlenmeyer flask containing 25 mL of 3% aqueous solution of boric acid, 0.04 mL of a mixture of methyl red and methylene blue indicators was used as the indicator. Distillation was continued until a final distillate volume of 125 mL was obtained. The distilled TVBN was titrated with an aqueous 0.1N HCL solution. TVBN content was expressed as mgN/100 g of fish flesh (Goulas and Kontominas, 2005). $TVBN = (V \times C \times 14 \times 100) / 10$, where V was the volume of hydrochloric acid added and its concentration (C), 10 represented the weight of the sample, while 14 is the molecular weight of nitrogen.

FFA determination

Percent FFA was determined by a Standard AACC method (AACC, 2004). The FFA was expressed as percent oleic acid equivalent.

Microbiological analyses

A 25-g fish sample from the dorsal region with skin on, was mixed with 225 mL of peptone water diluent, and homogenized. An estimation of the total viable counts that could be responsible partly for deterioration in quality both as a result of contamination due to poor handling and autolysis was made. The TVC and H₂S-producing bacteria counts were done on Iron Agar (Oxoid, UK) by pour plate technique with an overlay as described by Gram *et al.* (1987). The plates were incubated at 22 °C and 37 °C for 3 days. TVC was obtained by registering all bacterial colonies (colony forming units-CFU) on the incubated plates from each dilution of the sample showing growth. The number of colonies showing a clear dark colour represented the bacterial population able to produce H₂S, while the white colonies represented the TVC.

Data Analysis

ANOVA was performed on treatment means for each parameter studied using Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS 15, Chicago, Illinois) to examine whether there were significant differences in the parameters analyzed with storage time in ice and with treatment (gutting and ungutting).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sensory Evaluation

The quality index scheme developed for this study is shown in Table 1. There was an increase in in the QI scores with storage time in ice for both gutted and ungutted experimental (Table 2) and control Tilapia fish samples (Table 3); similar observations were apparent in the gutted and ungutted experimental and control Nile perch (Tables 4 and 5). The increases showed the progressive deterioration of the fish as shown in the sensory changes over the storage period. The highest QI scores for all the parameters for the ungutted experimental and control Tilapia samples were reached on day 22 (QI score, 16.02 out of a maximum score of 20) and day 30 (QI score, 17.85 out of a maximum score of 20) of storage in ice, respectively. For ungutted experimental and control Nile perch, the highest QI scores were reached on day 22 and 28 of storage in ice, respectively; at this point the fish was considered unfit for human consumption. Hygienic gutting increased the shelf life of both Tilapia and Nile perch bought from the beaches by approximately 4 days. The control samples of tilapia from the Dominion aquaculture farm had a longer shelf (30

days for ungutted as compared to the ungutted Nile perch controls which had a shelf life of 28 days). Hygienic gutting increased the shelf life of both Tilapia and Nile perch bought from the beaches by approximately 4 days. The control samples of tilapia from the Dominion aquaculture farm had a longer shelf (30 days for ungutted as compared to the Nile perch controls which had a shelf life of 28 days). The longer shelf life was probably due to the controlled icing which was done within 1 hr of harvest of the farmed tilapia. Guts removal slowed the rate of the observed sensory changes in both fish species, consequently resulting in extended prime quality and shelf life.

Biochemical Parameters

TVBN

The TVBN of the ungutted and gutted experimental Tilapia increased with storage time in ice (Figure 1). There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the values of this index from the 14th day of storage in ice for both the ungutted and gutted experimental Tilapia. However, these values were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) for the gutted experimental Tilapia as compared to the ungutted experimental Tilapia. The TVBN value at the end of shelf life (day 22) for the ungutted Tilapia was 26.54 mg N/100 g flesh, while for the gutted (day 26) was 19.20 mg N/100 g flesh. A significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in TVBN values was also observed with storage in ice for both the ungutted and gutted Nile perch with values of 26.03 and 24.52 mg N/100 g, respectively, at the end of the shelf life. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in TVBN values between the two species of fish at the end of shelf life. Significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in TVBN values was observed with storage in ice for both the ungutted and gutted Nile perch with values of 26.03 and 24.52 mg N/100 g, respectively, at the end of the shelf life in ice. The results showed that there was some similarity in the proteolytic activity that produced the TVBN in the two fish species, whose rate was slower in the gutted fish. Further, the levels of TVBN in hygienically gutted fish samples (compared to the ungutted fish) were lower due to the reduced gut microbial load and hence reduced bacterial decomposition of nitrogenous compounds in the fish flesh.

pH

In this study, pH was considered a factor that determines the survival and growth of micro-organisms during storage, processing and distribution of fish. The pH for the ungutted and gutted experimental Tilapia increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) from the 18th day of storage in ice (Figure 2), whereas a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in pH was observed from the 14th day in the Nile perch. For Tilapia, the significant increase occurred at pH 6.95 with the end at about 7.05 on day 28. For the Nile perch, the significant increase occurred at pH 6.9 ending at 7.1 and 7.2 for gutted and ungutted Nile perch, respectively, on day 28 of storage in ice. The pH at rejection point by the taste panel was almost similar for both species, irrespective of whether they were gutted or not. The increase in pH indicates the accumulation of volatile amines such as ammonia mainly derived from microbial actions through bacterial degradation or deamination of proteins, peptides and amino acids in the fish muscle. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in pH variation between the gutted and ungutted fish samples of each of the two fish species, showing that gutting does not significantly influence pH variation.

FFA

There was a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in FFA content of the ungutted and gutted Tilapia on the 14th and 18th day of storage in ice, respectively (Figure 3). Similar observations were apparent in the Nile perch, with a significance increase ($p < 0.05$) recorded on the 14th day for both the gutted and ungutted Nile perch. Although Nile perch had an initial FFA value of about 1.9 oleic acid equivalent, the values at rejection point on day 26 were 2.6 and 2.7 mg oleic acid equivalents for the gutted and ungutted fish. For Tilapia the initial values were about 1.7 mg oleic acid equivalents and 2.4 mg oleic acid equivalents on day 26 of storage for both gutted and ungutted fish. At the point of rejection for both fish species, %FFA values were 2.4-2.7 mg oleic acid equivalents. The progressive increase in the %FFA values over the storage time showed the progressive breakdown of lipids in fish muscle with time in ice. Gutting, however, reduced the rate of lipid breakdown and the subsequent formation of FFA in both fish species. However, the rate of FFA formation was greater in the Nile perch than in Tilapia for some unclear reason, despite both having a comparable total lipid content of 0.61% for Tilapia and 0.63% for Nile perch. Postmortem hydrolysis of fish muscle lipids leads to the release of free fatty acids. During storage, a considerable amount of FFA appears. This phenomenon is more profound in ungutted than gutted fish, and is catalyzed by lipases and phospholipases (Pacheco-Aguilar *et al.*, 2000). From the results of this work, the rate of breakdown of lipid to form FFA may vary

with fish species, although the content at the end of shelf life was of similar magnitude for each species (2.5-2.6% for gutted and gutted Nile perch and 2.1-2.2% FFA for ungutted and gutted Tilapia).

Microbiological Parameters

H₂S-producing Bacteria

A significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in H₂S-producing bacteria was observed in the ungutted Tilapia from the 14th day while in the gutted fish this was apparent from the 18th day of storage in ice onwards. There was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in levels of H₂S-producing bacteria between the gutted and ungutted Tilapia with higher levels being observed in the ungutted fish samples. The gutted and ungutted iced experimental Nile perch showed H₂S-producing bacteria counts that also increased significantly ($p < 0.05$). However, higher counts were observed at any one stage of storage in the ungutted Nile perch as compared to the gutted fish (Figure 4). At the point signifying the end of shelf life, the level of these bacteria was log 5.3 and log 5.6 in gutted and ungutted Tilapia, respectively, but log 5.5 and 6.5 in gutted and ungutted Nile perch, respectively. There was an observed increase in the hydrogen sulphide-producing bacteria load over the storage period in both gutted and ungutted Nile perch and Tilapia. The increase in the bacterial load in the gutted fish of both species was slower as a result of gut material removal. Guts are therefore sources of hydrogen sulphide-producing bacteria in the Nile perch and Tilapia. Despite different initial values of bacterial loads, the values at the end of shelf life were of similar magnitude (CFU log 5.1 and 6.5 for ungutted and gutted Nile perch, respectively, and log 5.3 and 5.1 for ungutted and gutted Tilapia, respectively). The magnitude of the counts in both fish species at the point of rejection by the taste panel was similar irrespective of whether they were gutted or not.

Coliforms

A significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in coliform count was observed in both gutted and ungutted fish samples as storage progressed in ice. The difference in coliform forming units between the gutted and the ungutted was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) in both fish species with higher values observed in the ungutted batch (Figure 2). This signifies that guts are sources of coliforms. At the point signifying the end of consumer acceptability, the coliforms count was log 2.0 (up from log 1.8) in gutted Tilapia as compared to log 5.1 (up from log 3.1) in the gutted Nile perch. The values in the ungutted Tilapia and Nile perch were log 5.0 (up from log 3.1 for Tilapia and log 2.8 in the Nile perch, respectively) (Figure 5). The removal of gut material considerably reduced the rate of increase of coliforms in both fish species. However, the level of coliforms at the end of shelf life was of similar magnitude for the ungutted and gutted fish of each fish species. Similar to the hydrogen sulphide-producing bacteria, guts are sources of coliforms. The high level of coliforms in both gutted and ungutted fish of both species is a cause for concern as far as food safety is concerned. The high levels may be attributed to the poor personal hygiene and poor hygiene standards on the artisanal, outrigger boats, high ambient water temperatures (21-24°C) and the poor handling before icing. For Tilapia, the initial CFU was log 1.5 and 2.2 but at the end of shelf life, the CFU was log 5.1 and 2.2 in ungutted and gutted Tilapia, respectively. But for Nile perch the initial values were CFU log 1.3 and 2.7 for gutted and ungutted, which were CFU log 1.8 and 5.1 on day 22, respectively. Therefore, the magnitude of the final level of coliforms at rejection point by the taste panel for both fish species was similar in the gutted and ungutted lots. There were no *E. coli* detected in both fish species over the entire storage period whether the fish were gutted or left ungutted.

Table 1-The QIM scheme developed for L. Victoria Nile perch (*Lates niloticus*) and Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) stored in ice

Parameters		Attributes	Demerit Points	
Appearance	Skin	Very bright, pearl shiny	0	
		Bright	1	
		Dull	2	
Eyes	Slime	Clear-transparent	0	
		Slightly cloudy/milky	1	
		Cloudy	2	
	Clarity	Clear-translucent	0	
		Slightly opaque	1	
		Opaque	2	
Texture	Shape	Convex	0	
		Flat	1	
		Concave/Sunken	2	
	Elasticity	Elastic	0	
		Slightly marked by pressure	1	
		Clearly marked by pressure	2	
Gills	Belly	Intact	0	
		Slightly intact	1	
		Soft	2	
	Colour	Very soft	3	
		Bright/dark red	0	
		Brownish red	1	
		Discoloured/brown	2	
		Gill Odour	Fresh/seaweedy	0
			Neutral	1
	Fishy/sour		2	
	Gill slime	Off-odour/rotten	3	
		Clear-translucent	0	
Slightly cloudy		1		
Cloudy		2		
Total demerit points(QI scores)			20	

Table 2-QI scores for sensory parameters of iced gutted and ungutted experimental L. Victoria tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

Parameters		Days of Sampling						
		2	6	10	14	18	22	26
Skin	G	0.5±0.35 ^a	0.6±0.17 ^a	0.75±0.25 ^a	1.38±0.15 ^b	1.6±0.01 ^b	1.63±0.11 ^b	2±0.01 ^c
	U	0.5±0.36 ^a	1.2±0.37 ^b	1.13±0.1 ^b	1.38±0.06 ^b	1.6±0.03 ^c	1.88±0.01 ^c	N/a
Slime	G	0.33±0.2 ^a	0.8±0.11 ^b	0.63±0.2 ^b	1±0.01 ^b	1.6±0.17 ^c	1.63±0.00 ^c	1.63±0.05 ^c
	U	0.5±0.36 ^a	0.8±0.34 ^a	0.75±0.6 ^a	1.25±0.31 ^b	1.6±0.41 ^b	1.63±0.10 ^b	N/a
Eyes clarity	G	0.33±0.06 ^a	0.4±0.01 ^a	0.5±0.4 ^a	1±0.2 ^b	1.2±0.12 ^b	1.25±0.02 ^b	1.38±0.16 ^b
	U	0±0.04 ^a	0.8±0.14 ^b	0.75±0.5 ^b	1.25±0.02 ^c	1.2±0.1 ^c	1.38±0.17 ^c	N/a
Eye shape	G	0±0.05 ^a	0.6±0.05 ^b	0.75±0.0 ^b	1±0.02 ^b	1.1±0.02 ^b	1.25±0.15 ^c	1.25±0.21 ^c
	U	0±0.05 ^a	1.1±0.01 ^b	1.00±0.14 ^b	1.13±0.12 ^b	1±0.05 ^b	1.13±0.06 ^b	N/a
Elasticity	G	0.17±0.01 ^a	0.4±0.11 ^b	0.63±0.08 ^b	0.88±0.22 ^b	1.4±0.16 ^c	1.63±0.04 ^c	1.88±0.11 ^c
	U	0.33±0.01 ^a	0.5±0.21 ^a	0.75±0.12 ^b	1.25±0.11 ^b	1.8±0.07 ^c	1.75±0.14 ^c	N/a
Belly	G	0.17±0.02 ^a	0.4±0.30 ^a	0.88±0.16 ^b	1.13±0.01 ^b	1.6±0.10 ^c	1.75±0.05 ^c	1.75±0.10 ^c
	U	0.83±0.05 ^a	0.8±0.02 ^a	1.38±0.02 ^a	1.63±0.05 ^b	2±0.2 ^b	2.00±0.22 ^b	N/a
Gill color	G	0.33±0.11 ^a	0.5±0.05 ^a	1.25±0.16 ^b	1.13±0.17 ^b	1.6±0.01 ^c	1.5±0.12 ^c	1.88±0.05 ^c
	U	1±1.10 ^a	0.8±0.49 ^a	1.25±0.02 ^a	1.25±0.07 ^a	1.6±0.15 ^b	1.50±0.05 ^b	N/a
Gill odor	G	0.17±0.15 ^a	0.4±0.07 ^a	1±0.05 ^b	1±0.01 ^b	2±0.02 ^c	2.13±0.10 ^c	2±0.01 ^c
	U	0.68±0.25 ^a	0.7±0.33 ^a	1.25±0.21 ^b	1.38±0.06 ^b	2.4±0.06 ^c	2.75±0.02 ^c	N/a
Gill slime	G	0.33±0.02 ^a	0.7±0.04 ^b	0.75±0.2 ^b	1.13±0.21 ^b	1.2±0.30 ^b	2±0.01 ^c	2±0.12 ^c
	U	0.68±0.12 ^a	0.6±0.10 ^a	0.75±0.04 ^a	1.25±0.02 ^b	1.6±0.10 ^b	2.00±0.3 ^c	N/a

Mean values in the same row with the same superscript are not significantly different ($p>0.05$). Legend: G-gutted, U-ungutted

Table 3-QI scores for sensory parameters of iced gutted and ungutted farmed Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

Parameters	Days of Sampling									
	2	6	10	14	18	22	26	30	32	
Skin G	0±0.01 ^a	0.2±0.2 ^a	0.5±0.5 ^a	1.25±0.08 ^b	1.3±0.11 ^b	1.63±0.33 ^c	1.63±0.09 ^c	1.86±0.21 ^c	1.63±0.14 ^c	
	U	0±0.11 ^a	0.2±0.4 ^a	0.75±0.11 ^b	1.38±0.12 ^b	1.5±0.02 ^c	1.88±0.21 ^c	2±0.18 ^c	2±0.13 ^c	N/a
Slime G	0.33±0.24 ^a	0.6±0.11 ^a	0.5±0.2 ^a	1.13±0.05 ^b	1.6±0.04 ^b	1.38±0.05 ^b	1.67±0.03 ^b	1.71±0.15 ^b	2±0.05 ^c	
	U	0±0.31 ^a	0.4±0.2 ^a	0.5±0.17 ^a	1.63±0.11 ^b	1.6±0.1 ^b	1.38±0.08 ^b	1.83±0.16 ^b	1.86±0.34 ^b	N/a
Eye clarity G	0.33±0.05 ^a	0.4±0.15 ^a	0.5±0.02 ^a	1.25±0.16 ^b	1.2±0.22 ^b	1.38±0.01 ^b	1.67±0.05 ^b	1.71±0.17 ^b	1.88±0.05 ^b	
	U	0.33±0.07 ^a	0.4±0.22 ^a	0.63±0.0 ^a	1.38±0.33 ^b	1.4±0.18 ^b	1.63±0.06 ^b	1.67±0.01 ^b	1.71±0.06 ^b	N/a
Eye shape G	0±0.21 ^a	0.4±0.01 ^a	0.63±0.05 ^a	1±0.2 ^b	1±0.15 ^b	1.63±0.02 ^c	1.33±0.3 ^b	1.57±0.10 ^b	1.88±0.01 ^c	
	U	0.33±0.0 ^a	0.6±0.11 ^a	0.63±0.13 ^a	0.88±0.16 ^a	1.6±0.06 ^b	1.63±0.14 ^b	1.83±0.15 ^b	1.71±0.09 ^b	N/a
Elasticity G	0.17±0.12 ^a	0.2±0.18 ^a	0.38±0.08 ^a	1.13±0.21 ^b	1±0.14 ^b	1.25±0.1 ^b	1.5±0.04 ^b	1.57±0.5 ^c	1.75±0.1 ^c	
	U	0.17±0.14 ^a	0.4±0.05 ^a	0.5±0.04 ^a	1.38±0.03 ^b	1.6±0.01 ^b	1.88±0.02 ^c	1.67±0.02 ^b	1.71±0.33 ^b	N/a
Belly G	0.17±0.05 ^a	0.2±0.12 ^a	0.63±0.24 ^b	1.13±0.13 ^b	1.4±0.2 ^b	1.25±0.18 ^b	1.67±0.17 ^c	1.71±0.12 ^c	2±0.04 ^c	
	U	0.33±0.01 ^a	0.4±0.01 ^a	0.75±0.06 ^b	1.63±0.0 ^b	1.8±0.17 ^c	1.63±0.11 ^b	1.83±0.17 ^c	2±0.14 ^c	N/a
Gill color G	0.17±0.17 ^a	0.4±0.06 ^b	0.63±0.05 ^b	1.63±0.05 ^c	1.4±0.11 ^c	1.75±0.05 ^c	1.83±0.11 ^c	1.86±0.05 ^c	1.85±0.06 ^c	
	U	0.17±0.04 ^a	0.4±0.0 ^b	0.63±0.1 ^b	1.38±0.07 ^c	1.4±0.01 ^c	1.75±0.06 ^c	2±0.01 ^d	1.86±0.07 ^c	N/a
Gill odor G	0.17±0.02 ^a	0.5±0.16 ^b	0.88±0.14 ^b	1.38±0.12 ^c	1.6±0.04 ^c	1.63±0.12 ^c	2±0.01 ^c	2±0.16 ^c	3±0.17 ^d	
	U	0.17±0.02 ^a	0.4±0.01 ^b	0.75±0.01 ^b	1.88±0.34 ^c	1.7±0.21 ^c	1.88±0.1 ^c	2±0.41 ^c	3±0.38 ^d	N/a
Gill slime G	0.33±0.33 ^a	0.5±0.1 ^a	0.63±0.07 ^a	1.38±0.14 ^b	1.2±0.07 ^b	1.75±0.08 ^b	1.5±0.08 ^b	1.86±0.18 ^c	2±0.05 ^c	
	U	0.33±0.01 ^a	0.6±0.13 ^a	0.75±0.05 ^a	1.63±0.18 ^b	1.7±0.01 ^b	1.88±0.05 ^b	1.88±0.04 ^b	2±0.14 ^b	N/a

Mean values in the same row with the same superscript are not significantly different ($p>0.05$). Legend: G-gutted, U-ungutted

Table 4-QI scores for sensory parameters of iced gutted and ungutted experimental Nile perch (*Lates niloticus*)

Parameters		Days of sampling						
		2	6	10	14	18	22	26
Skin	G.	0.45±0.13 ^a	0.60±0.13 ^a	0.75±0.11 ^a	0.96±0.04 ^b	1.1±0.11 ^b	1.47±0.23 ^b	1.87±0.12 ^c
	U.	0.43±0.15 ^a	0.77±0.15 ^a	0.83±0.11 ^a	0.97±0.05 ^a	1.1±0.1 ^b	1.53±0.57 ^b	N/a
Slime	G.	0.43±0.10 ^a	0.61±0.14 ^a	0.71±0.15 ^a	1.17±0.15 ^b	1.41±0.10 ^b	1.63±0.11 ^b	1.92±0.12 ^c
	U	0.33±0.10 ^a	0.70±0.17 ^a	1.07±0.15 ^b	1.47±0.12 ^b	1.83±0.15 ^b	1.93±0.12 ^c	N/a
Eyes clarity.	G.	0.33±0.01 ^a	0.37±0.12 ^a	0.73±0.10 ^a	1.03±0.12 ^b	1.37±0.15 ^b	1.53±0.12 ^b	1.91±0.15 ^c
	U	0.40±0.00 ^a	0.73±0.23 ^a	1.0±0.00 ^b	1.23±0.15 ^b	1.67±0.21 ^b	1.93±0.12 ^c	N/a
Eyes shape	G.	0.27±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.15 ^a	0.81±0.12 ^a	1.10±0.05 ^a	1.40±0.10 ^b	1.61±0.14 ^b	1.90±0.10 ^c
	U	0.20±0.02 ^a	0.37±0.20 ^a	1.03±0.15 ^b	0.93±0.02 ^a	1.7±0.17 ^b	1.9±0.10 ^b	N/a
Elasticity	G.	0.25±0.11 ^a	0.33±0.11 ^a	0.78±0.16 ^a	1.20±0.10 ^b	1.50±0.11 ^b	1.73±0.02 ^b	1.93±0.02 ^b
	U	0.27±0.15 ^a	0.47±0.23 ^a	0.9±0.26 ^b	1.47±0.05 ^b	1.67±0.21 ^b	1.97±0.02 ^c	N/a
Belly	G.	0.30±0.21 ^a	0.55±0.15 ^a	0.73±0.18 ^a	1.25±0.12 ^b	1.91±0.22 ^b	2.31±0.21 ^c	2.70±0.07 ^c
	U	0.37±0.23 ^a	0.83±0.25 ^a	1.23±0.25 ^b	1.5±0.10 ^b	2.2±0.26 ^c	2.57±0.41 ^c	N/a
Gill color	G.	0.37±0.13 ^a	0.55±0.25 ^a	0.81±0.13 ^a	1.04±0.13 ^a	1.32±0.15 ^b	1.57±0.12 ^b	1.90±0.12 ^c
	U	0.43±0.23 ^a	0.83±0.4 ^a	0.93±0.23 ^b	1.26±0.23 ^b	1.4±0.26 ^b	1.70±0.10 ^b	N/a
Gill odor	G.	0.30±0.15 ^a	0.43±0.12 ^a	0.70±0.10 ^a	1.41±0.15 ^b	1.53±0.21 ^b	2.25±0.25 ^c	2.71±0.08 ^c
	U	0.33±0.15 ^a	0.63±0.11 ^a	1.00±0.10 ^b	1.60±0.20 ^b	2.0±0.65 ^c	2.57±0.45 ^c	N/a
Gill slime	G.	0.45±0.15 ^a	0.63±0.15 ^a	0.89±0.03 ^a	1.53±0.12 ^b	1.48±0.11 ^b	1.63±0.12 ^b	1.94±0.08 ^c
	U	0.43±0.15 ^a	0.83±0.15 ^a	0.97±0.02 ^b	1.33±0.14 ^b	1.87±0.05 ^b	1.93±0.11 ^c	N/a
QI scores	G.	3.23±0.15 ^a	4.37±0.81 ^a	6.91±0.85 ^a	10.49±1.20 ^b	13.24±0.75 ^b	15.73±0.5 ^b	18.78±0.4 ^c
	U	3.3±0.45 ^a	6.2±0.96 ^a	9.1±0.75 ^b	12.03±0.23 ^b	15.6±1.05 ^b	18.1±0.5 ^c	N/a

Mean values in the same row with the same superscript are not significantly different ($p>0.05$). Legend: G-gutted, U-ungutted

Table 5-QI scores for sensory parameters of iced gutted and ungutted control L. Victoria Nile perch (*Lates niloticus*) Values in the same row with the same superscript are not significantly different ($p>0.05$). Legend: G-gutted, U-ungutted

Parameters		Days of sampling							
		2	6	10	14	18	22	26	28
Skin	G	0.70±0.20 ^a	0.80±0.30 ^a	0.70±0.05 ^a	1.00±0.05 ^a	1.10±0.30 ^b	1.25±0.10 ^b	1.50±0.03 ^b	1.73±0.05 ^b
	U	0.73±0.30 ^a	0.80±0.30 ^a	1.00±0.05 ^a	1.00±0.05 ^b	1.23±0.30 ^b	1.37±0.1 ^b	1.70±0.03 ^b	2.00±0.00 ^c
Slime	G	0.10±0.10 ^a	0.30±0.10 ^a	0.80±0.05 ^a	1.00±0.05 ^a	1.10±0.20 ^b	1.37±0.10 ^b	1.56±0.05 ^b	1.71±0.03 ^b
	U	0.26±0.05 ^a	0.40±0.10 ^a	1.00±0.05 ^a	1.00±0.05 ^b	1.33±0.20 ^b	1.57±0.1 ^b	1.86±0.05 ^b	2.00±0.00 ^c
Eyes Clarity	G	0.30±0.10 ^a	0.40±0.05 ^a	0.80±0.02 ^a	1.10±0.05 ^a	1.20±0.06 ^b	1.43±0.10 ^b	1.57±0.01 ^b	1.72±0.04 ^b
	U	0.46±0.05 ^a	0.47±0.05 ^a	1.00±0.02 ^a	1.27±0.05 ^b	1.27±0.06 ^b	1.63±0.1 ^b	1.77±0.01 ^b	2.00±0.00 ^c
Eyes shape	G	0.25±0.02 ^a	0.30±0.04 ^a	0.63±0.11 ^a	0.95±0.20 ^a	1.17±0.11 ^a	1.35±0.05 ^b	1.51±0.01 ^b	1.69±0.02 ^b
	U	0.20±0.02 ^a	0.57±0.04 ^a	1.33±0.11 ^a	1.27±0.20 ^b	1.37±0.11 ^b	1.50±0.05 ^b	1.77±0.01 ^b	2.00±0.00 ^c
Elasticity	G	0.21±0.05 ^a	0.30±0.10 ^a	0.70±0.10 ^a	1.07±0.11 ^a	1.30±0.05 ^b	1.43±0.01 ^b	1.61±0.22 ^b	1.71±0.02 ^b
	U	0.23±0.05 ^a	0.30±0.10 ^a	0.80±0.10 ^a	1.07±0.11 ^b	1.30±0.05 ^b	1.43±0.01 ^b	1.87±0.22 ^b	2.00±0.00 ^c
Belly	G	0.62±0.03 ^a	0.49±0.23 ^a	1.00±0.28 ^a	1.23±0.06 ^b	1.41±0.05 ^b	1.61±0.10 ^b	1.95±0.11 ^b	2.15±0.30 ^c
	U	1.34±0.03 ^a	1.49±0.23 ^a	1.63±0.28 ^a	1.73±0.06 ^b	1.86±0.05 ^b	1.98±0.10 ^b	2.05±0.11 ^b	2.17±0.30 ^b
Gill Color	G	0.43±0.25 ^a	0.47±0.23 ^a	0.63±0.11 ^a	1.00±0.23 ^a	1.27±0.15 ^b	1.31±0.05 ^b	1.53±0.25 ^b	1.69±0.04 ^b
	U	0.47±0.25 ^a	0.47±0.23 ^a	1.06±0.11 ^a	1.13±0.23 ^b	1.33±0.15 ^b	1.46±0.05 ^b	1.77±0.25 ^b	2.00±0.00 ^c
Gill Odor	G	0.21±0.05 ^a	0.53±0.05 ^a	0.82±0.15 ^a	1.23±0.15 ^b	1.41±0.20 ^b	1.53±0.40 ^b	1.93±0.30 ^b	2.25±0.11 ^c
	U	0.20±0.05 ^a	0.53±0.05 ^a	1.17±0.15 ^a	1.33±0.15 ^b	1.50±0.20 ^b	1.70±0.40 ^b	2.13±0.30 ^b	2.93±0.11 ^c
Gill Slime	G	0.25±0.05 ^a	0.41±0.17 ^a	0.71±0.05 ^a	1.00±0.15 ^a	1.21±0.06 ^b	1.45±0.20 ^b	1.60±0.11 ^b	1.73±0.02 ^b
	U	0.27±0.05 ^a	0.40±0.17 ^a	1.00±0.05 ^a	1.20±0.15 ^b	1.27±0.06 ^b	1.70±0.20 ^b	1.93±0.11 ^c	2.00±0.02 ^c
QI scores	G	3.07±0.34 ^a	4.0±0.33 ^a	6.79±0.44 ^a	9.58±0.17 ^a	11.17±0.47 ^b	12.73±0.2 ^b	14.7±0.22 ^b	16.4±0.1 ^b
	U	3.37±0.78 ^a	4.53±0.83 ^a	9.30±0.44 ^a	10.5±0.17 ^b	12.13±0.47 ^b	14.33±0.6 ^b	16.6±0.26 ^b	19.0±0.10 ^c

Figure 1-Effect of gutting on changes in TVBN in iced Nile perch and Nile tilapia

Figure 2-Effect of gutting on changes in pH in iced Nile perch and Nile tilapia

Figure 3-Effect of gutting on changes in FFA in iced Nile perch and Nile tilapia

Figure 4-Effect of gutting on H₂S-producing bacterial load in iced Nile perch and Nile tilapia

Figure 5-Effect of gutting on coliforms load in iced Nile perch and Nile tilapia

CONCLUSIONS

Gutting increased the shelf life of both the Nile perch and Tilapia by about 4 days as a result of the reduced bacterial load in the guts. Both the content and rate of multiplication of coliforms and hydrogen sulphide producing bacteria reduced after gutting. Similarly, the increase in TVBN, FFA and pH in both fish species slowed over the storage period as a result of gutting. Therefore gutting can enable iced tropical fish retain prime quality for longer and extend its shelf life in ice.

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